

Subtitling for language acquisition: Eye tracking as predictor of attention allocation in education

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This paper focuses on the cognitive effectiveness of watching subtitled discipline-specific videos to determine how subtitling, as an emerging technology, encourages language equity, social justice, and the rise of technomultilingualism. Cognitive effectiveness is investigated using gaze duration in eye-tracking as a proxy for attention allocation and gist comprehension together with scene and word recognition. It also considers whether academic English subtitles permit students enough time to look at both on-screen images and text. This study uses eye-tracking data from seven student participants in the Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences at the University of Pretoria. The students were offered subtitles in English, Afrikaans, isiZulu, and Sepedi. However, the participants who volunteered for the study selected largely English and Afrikaans subtitles, and the isiZulu and Sepedi subtitles were unfortunately not utilised during this particular study. This paper concludes that the participants preferred English subtitles and remembered certain concepts from the videos better when their focus was on the subtitles themselves rather than exclusively on the on-screen image.

Keywords: Cognitive Effectiveness; Eye-Tracking; Gaze Duration; Language Equity; Multilingualism; Social Justice; Subtitles; Technomultilingualism

1. Introduction

Eye-tracking technology has been increasingly utilised in second language acquisition research, providing insight into how students process written texts and speech in real-time (Conklin & Pellicer-Sánchez, 2016; Eckstein et al., 2023; Okuizumi, 2020). One of the areas where eye-tracking has been used extensively is in the investigation of the impact of subtitles on language learning. Subtitles are commonly used in language teaching and learning as they provide a visual aid that can enhance comprehension, especially for students with limited proficiency in the target language (Kruger-Roux & Angu, 2020). However, there has been debate about the effectiveness of subtitles as a language-learning tool, and eye-tracking studies have helped shed light on this issue.

This article reviews and analyses existing literature on subtitle eye-tracking and its role in language acquisition, comprehension, and cognitive effectiveness to contextualise an eye-tracking study using data gathered from seven students in the Faculty of Natural and Agricultural Sciences at the University of Pretoria. The students were offered subtitles in English, Afrikaans, isiZulu, and Sepedi. It should be noted, however, that the participants who volunteered for this study only made use of the English and Afrikaans subtitles, and the isiZulu and Sepedi subtitles were unfortunately not used during this study. This study describes some of the effects of subtitles on language learning, focusing on the factors that influence the efficacy of subtitles, such as text type, language proficiency, and cognitive effectiveness. The study focuses on the cognitive effectiveness of watching subtitled, discipline-specific videos to determine how subtitling, as an emerging technology, encourages language equity, social justice, and the rise of technomultilingualism (Ndlangamandla, 2022);¹ technomultilingualism is a term which emphasises the link between literacy and technology (Ndlangamandla, 2022). It is claimed that analysing students' eye movements when engaging with academic subtitles could expand on this notion, considering the turn to online or hybrid education by many higher education institutions during the Covid-19 pandemic. In the current study, cognitive effectiveness is investigated using gaze duration in eye-tracking as a proxy for attention allocation and gist comprehension together with scene and word recognition (Perego et al., 2010). Additionally, this article considers whether academic English subtitles permit students enough time to look at both on-screen images and text. Finally, the implications of subtitle eye-tracking research for language teaching and learning will be discussed.

2. Background

Eye-tracking technology involves using specialised equipment to measure the movements of the eyes as a person reads or views a visual stimulus. By recording the duration and location of fixations, researchers can gain insight into the cognitive processes involved in language comprehension. Eye-tracking can provide information on how readers allocate their attention to different parts of a (visual) text, how long they spend on each part, and how they simultaneously process visual and textual information (Conklin & Pellicer-Sánchez, 2016).

Subtitle eye-tracking studies have focused on investigating the effects of subtitles on language learning (Liao et al., 2021). Subtitles have been found to improve comprehension of foreign-language films or TV programmes, as they provide students with visual cues to help them understand the meaning of unfamiliar words or phrases (Birulés-Muntané & Soto-Faraco, 2016). However, the effectiveness of subtitles depends on various factors, such as the

complexity of the text, the learner's proficiency, and the cognitive load imposed by the text and visual stimuli (Kruger & Doherty, 2016). Eye-tracking studies have provided valuable insights into these factors and how they affect the processing of subtitles. In other words, subtitle eye-tracking research has provided valuable insights into the cognitive processes involved in language acquisition and the effectiveness of subtitles as a language learning tool. By examining the factors that influence the processing of subtitles, researchers can help improve the design of language teaching materials and enhance language learning outcomes. Integrating eye-tracking technology into language acquisition research has opened up new avenues for investigating language learning processes.

Eye-tracking, subtitling, and multilingualism are three research areas that have garnered increasing attention in recent years. The use of subtitles has become ubiquitous in global film and television industries to reach wider audiences. However, reading subtitles can be complex for multilingual audiences, requiring significant cognitive effort and impacting viewer attention and comprehension. Eye-tracking technology has emerged as a promising tool for understanding the cognitive processes involved in subtitle reading and has been used in several studies to investigate the effects of subtitling on multilingualism. This literature review aims to examine the current state of research in eye-tracking, subtitling, and multilingualism, focusing on studies that have used eye-tracking to investigate the effects of subtitling on multilingualism. It should be noted that studies with deaf and hard-of-hearing subjects have been excluded in this review as they do not pertain to the current study.

Eye-tracking technology has been used extensively in research on reading and language processing. Eye-tracking allows researchers to track eye movements during reading, providing insights into the cognitive processes involved in comprehension. For multilingual readers, eye-tracking offers a unique opportunity to investigate the cognitive processes of reading subtitles in a second language. Several studies have used eye-tracking to investigate the effects of subtitling on multilingualism.

A study by Kruger et al. (2013) examined the effects of subtitling on first-language (L1) and second-language (L2) English speakers' visual attention. The study used eye-tracking to determine how participants' visual attention was divided between on-screen text (in the form of subtitles) and visuals. It found that there is definitely a great need for L1 and L2 subtitles in academic settings. The authors also considered cognitive load in multilingual educational settings, suggesting that it may occur when viewers are forced to divide their attention between information sources, especially if some of these sources are superfluous (Kruger et al., 2013). They found that subtitles, however, do not

necessarily contribute to cognitive overload. The concept of cognitive load is discussed in detail in the results and findings section of this article.

Another relevant study based in South Africa is that of Matthew (2019). It considers how subtitles impact cognitive load by measuring participants' information-processing abilities and the impact of various subtitles using eye-tracking as a method to measure this data. This study found that subtitles do not impact cognitive load significantly. Matthew (2020) also investigated the impact of same-language subtitles (SLS) on "non-native" English speakers in South Africa. This study focused specifically on viewers in an e-learning setting and found that subtitled content had ". . . no significant effect either on performance or on perceived cognitive load for the students watching a recorded lecture with added subtitles compared to watching without subtitles" (Matthew, 2020, p. 1).

Lacroix (2012) focused on the effects of SLS on comprehension for students who spoke English as an additional language in a South African context. The study found that SLS are helpful in the context of discipline-specific comprehension, especially if viewers are made comfortable with subtitles as a mode of academic intervention. A few years earlier, Kruger and Kruger (2004) had concluded in their study that subtitling could potentially direct attention to issues connected specifically to language (particularly in the case of institutions where English is the medium of instruction). These issues include ". . . inaccessibility of information and illiteracy," and the authors asserted that addressing these issues will aid ". . . in the implementation of language rights and the promotion of multilingualism" (Kruger & Kruger, 2004, p. 111). This assertion highlights another important benefit of subtitled materials in multilingual education settings in South Africa—namely, improved inclusion of those who have been previously excluded from certain forms of information due to language barriers (Kruger & Kruger, 2004). Lastly, Kruger and Steyn (2013) investigated, through eye-tracking, the impact of SLS on academic performance. The study concludes that SLS did have a positive impact on comprehension and could therefore be a useful tool for "... reading instruction and language learning" (Kruger & Steyn, 2013, p. 105).

The present study differs from the various South African studies reviewed above in that subtitles other than exclusively SLS were used. Due to the participation of L2 students in the present study, their viewing interactions could also be measured with eye-tracking technology. By focusing on multilingual subtitles, this study is set apart from other studies in the South African higher education context. The present study highlights that academic subtitles, in conjunction with eye-tracking studies, can be important for multilingual students for several reasons, including comprehension and retention, language acquisition, and visual attention.

For students who are studying a discipline in which they are inexperienced or a discipline with many new terms, watching videos with subtitles can be a helpful tool for improving comprehension, especially for L2 students. However, if the students are struggling to keep up with the subtitles, they may miss important parts of the content (Van Der Zee et al., 2017). Along the same lines, Koolstra and Beentjes (1999) argued that multilingual students can improve their language acquisition skills through subtitle reading. As such, eye-tracking might help identify where students are looking on the screen, how much time they spend reading subtitles, and which parts of the subtitles they find most challenging. It is, therefore, hypothesized that eye-tracking studies can help identify where students are looking on the screen and how much time they spend reading subtitles; this can provide insights into how to optimise subtitle design for improved comprehension and retention of important information.

Eye-tracking can also provide insights into students' visual attention and focus. If students are struggling to keep up with subtitles or are distracted by other elements on the screen, this can impact their overall comprehension and engagement (Karamitroglou, 1997). Eye-tracking can help identify areas where students may be losing focus, which can inform instructional strategies and video design. Overall, subtitle eye-tracking can provide valuable information for optimising subtitle design to improve comprehension and retention, language acquisition, and visual attention for multilingual students.

3. Method

The current study provided its seven participants with subtitles in English, Afrikaans, isiZulu, and Sepedi. Among the participants, five were English L1 speakers, while two were English L2 speakers. Tracking the L2 participants' eye movements as they watched videos subtitled in both English and their L1 proved useful in determining which parts of the English subtitles they struggled with. There are, therefore, seven data points in total for the videos subtitled in English.

3.1. Instrument

The current study used the *Tobii X3-120* eye-tracking device for purposes of data collection. As stated earlier, eye-tracking is a technology used to measure the movement of a person's eyes and understand where they are looking. This technology works by using special cameras and software to track the position and movements of the eyes in real-time (Carter & Luke, 2020). The most common method of eye-tracking uses infrared light to illuminate the eye, which is then detected by a camera or cameras placed around the viewer's head. These cameras capture the reflection of the infrared light on the cornea and pupil, which allows the software to determine the exact position of the eye in

three dimensions (Carter & Luke, 2020). The software then uses this information to create a gaze map or gaze plot, which shows where the user is looking on a screen or in their environment (Santhoshikka et al., 2021). This map can be used to understand how the user is interacting with digital content, in this case, an academic video. The equipment can also record data about the timing and location of fixations and saccades, as well as measuring other eye-related parameters, such as blink rate, pupil dilation, and fixation duration (Carter & Luke, 2020). These parameters can provide additional insights into the viewer's behaviour and engagement.

Fixations and saccades are two important concepts in eye-tracking. A fixation is a period of time when the eye is relatively still and focused on a particular location or object. During a fixation, the eye is able to extract visual information from the environment, and this information is sent to the brain for processing (Carter & Luke, 2020). Typically, fixations last between 100 and 300 milliseconds, although they can be longer or shorter depending on the task or context (Galley et al., 2015). A saccade is a rapid, jolting movement of the eye that shifts its focus from one point to another. Saccades are used to move the fovea (the central part of the retina that provides the clearest and most detailed visual information) to different locations in the visual field so that new information can be processed (Carter & Luke, 2020). Saccades typically last between 20 and 200 milliseconds, depending on their length and direction (Rayner, 2009).

3.2. Procedure

Using *Tobii X3-120* eye-tracking device, the present study was conducted among seven participants ($N=7$) in a faculty of natural and agricultural sciences at a South African university. The participants were shown a discipline-specific video from one of their animal anatomy modules with subtitles available in English, Afrikaans, isiZulu, and Sepedi. Due to the demographics of the class from which participants volunteered, the only English L2 speakers who participated in the study were Afrikaans L1 speakers. Therefore, the isiZulu and Sepedi subtitles were unfortunately not utilised during this particular study. Before the video commenced, participants were introduced to the *Tobii X3-120* eye-tracking device. The participant would place the eye-tracking glasses linked to the device on their face, after which they were asked to focus on a specific image so that the device could be calibrated to their eyes. Once the device was calibrated and the participant was comfortable, the video began.

The English L1 participants only watched the video with English subtitles, while the English L2 speakers alternated between Afrikaans and English subtitles. The participants were allowed to view the video more than once. After watching the video, all participants were asked a series of questions

relating to the content discussed in the video, the contents of the subtitles, and events in the video. Appendix A presents the questions the participants were asked along with their correct answers. Participants were provided with answers in multiple-choice format.

Once each participant had finished watching the video and completed the short questions (see Appendix A), heat maps and gaze plots of their eye movements were generated using the program *Tobii Pro Lab*, version 1.194 (Tobii Pro AB, 2014). The results garnered from these heat maps and gaze plots will be analysed in the results and findings section of this paper. Below are examples of a gaze plot (Figure 1) and a heat map (Figure 2) produced by *Tobii Pro Lab*:

Figure 1 shows a gaze plot generated by *Tobii Pro Lab* based on the subject-specific video shown to participants in this study. Gaze plots are a type of visualisation used in eye-tracking studies to display the eye movement patterns of a person while they are engaged in a particular task, such as reading or viewing a video. Gaze plots provide a detailed view of where a person's eyes are fixating and how long they are fixating on each location (Santhoshikka et al., 2021). To

create a gaze plot, the eye-tracking software records the position of a participant's gaze over time as they view a stimulus—in this case, a subject-specific video. The resulting data is then plotted as a series of dots or circles on a grid that represents the visual stimulus. Each circle on the grid represents a fixation or a period of time when the participant's eyes were stationary on a particular location (Santhoshikka et al., 2021). The size of each circle corresponds to the duration of the fixation, with longer fixations represented by larger circles. The location of each circle indicates the position of the person's gaze during the fixation. Each participant is represented by a different colour on the gaze plot, and the order in which they viewed each stimulus is indicated by the numbers inside each circle on the gaze plot. By examining gaze plots, researchers can gain insight into a viewer's visual processing and attention allocation processes. The gaze plots generated from the current study have been valuable in the process of identifying patterns of fixation that suggest particular areas of interest or points of confusion in the video. This information can also be gathered from heat maps, as shown in Figure 2.

Figure 1.

An Example of a Gaze Plot Generated by the Tobii Pro Lab Program, Version 1.194

Similar to gaze plots, heat maps (e.g., Figure 2) are generated in eye-tracking by recording and analysing the movements of a given viewer's eyes as they view a visual stimulus. The eye-tracking device records the gaze data, which includes the location and duration of fixations (when the eyes are relatively stationary and focused on a specific point), saccades (when the eyes move quickly between different points), and also blinks (Santhoshikka et al., 2021).

Figure 2.
An Example of a Heat Map Generated by the Tobii Pro Lab Program, Version 1.194

To generate a heat map, the gaze data is aggregated and visualised using a colour scale that represents the intensity of eye movements in different areas of the stimulus. Typically, areas of the stimulus that receive more or longer fixations are represented by warmer colours (e.g., red, orange, or yellow), while areas with fewer or shorter fixations are represented by cooler colours (e.g., green). The resulting heat map provides a visual representation of the areas of the stimulus that captured the viewer's attention and engagement.

In the following section, heat maps and gaze plots generated by *Tobii Pro Lab* will be analysed in relation to participants' responses to post-video questions (Appendix A). After they had watched the video subtitled in English, the respondents' responses were recorded. Their answers were then compared to those of the L2 participants after watching the video with Afrikaans subtitles; then the heat maps and gaze plots produced by *Tobii Pro Lab* were analysed based on screenshots from the particular time stamp in the video to which each question refers. The seven participants were numbered P1 to P7; likewise, to refer to their viewing of the video with Afrikaans subtitles, the English L2 speakers were numbered P1 (L2) and P2 (L2).

4. Results and discussion

The questions (Appendix A) the participants were asked after viewing the video related to both the content discussed in the video itself and certain events or images in the video. This was done to determine whether there was any correlation between where participants focused their attention in the

video and their ability to comprehend and recall specific information and events from the video. This section will examine the L1 participants' responses to some of the questions in Appendix A in relation to their gaze plot and heat map activity. This information will then be compared to the responses of the L2 participants. It should be noted that, as mentioned earlier in this paper, the L2 participants watched the video with both English subtitles and subtitles in their L1. There are, therefore, seven total data points for the English-subtitled videos.

Four of the participants (57.14%) did not answer question 1 correctly. Examining their viewing activity using both the gaze plots and heat maps gives an insight into why these participants might have answered the question incorrectly.

Figure 3.
Gaze Plot for Question 1

Figure 4.
Heat Map for Question 1

As is shown in Figure 3, the participants watching the video subtitled in English did not fixate on the subtitles in this section of the video for very long. The only participants who paid attention to the subtitles were P3 (light blue) and P5 (yellow). Both of these participants answered the question correctly. However, these participants did not fixate on the subtitles for very long, as is indicated by the size of the fixation circles in Figure 3. Most of the participants seemed to focus on where the presenter was pointing. This correlates with the corresponding heat map from this section of the video (Figure 4). Interestingly, as indicated by the percentage of correct answers given to question 1, most of the participants could not remember the name of the structure discussed in the section of the video illustrated in Figures 3 and 4, even though they were fixated on its image—as indicated by the red areas of the heat map in Figure 4. However, the participants who did pay attention to the name of the discussed structure in the subtitles were able to name it correctly after the video had ended, even though they did not fixate on the information for long, as indicated by the green areas over the subtitles in Figure 4. This could indicate that

engaging with academic subtitles does assist content recall and possibly comprehension on some level.

For question 1 of the questionnaire (Appendix A), only data for the English-subtitled version of the video is available. This is because both of the Afrikaans L1 participants switched back to English subtitles at different points in the video. This is interesting when considering the rise of technomultilingualism (Ndlangamandla, 2022). While it may involve code-switching or code-mixing (in writing, in this case), technomultilingualism could be applied in this instance as well, as the L2 students preferred to switch back and forth between English and Afrikaans subtitles (Ndlangamandla, 2022). However, it must be considered that this behaviour may also be due to social pressures and expectations that people should be proficient in reading and understanding English, especially if they are studying at an English-medium higher education institution. Some people may also feel embarrassed because they believe that it is a basic skill that they should have already mastered, and this may not be something that the participants would freely admit to the researcher. It may be that students would prefer to engage with subtitles in their home language in an environment where they are afforded privacy and feel free from societal judgement.

Needless to say, cognitive load also must briefly be discussed in this context. Cognitive load refers to the amount of mental effort or resources required to process information in working memory. In other words, it refers to the amount of mental 'labour' involved in learning or completing a task (Kruger et al., 2013). Cognitive load theory suggests that there are limits to how much information the human brain can process at once. When the cognitive load is too high, it can lead to decreased performance, difficulty in learning, and mental fatigue (Kruger et al., 2013). Cognitive load is an important consideration here, as the English subtitles for the section of the video pertaining to question 1 were longer (57 characters, 1 line) than the Afrikaans subtitles for this section (48 characters, 1 line). Despite their longer lengths, the L2 participants still preferred to engage with the English subtitles in this particular part of the video. This behaviour concurs with the assertion by Kruger et al. (2013) that SLS in educational settings do not lead to heightened cognitive load but rather minimise it.

The purpose of question 2 in the questionnaire (Appendix A) was to determine whether the subtitles posed a distraction to the participants when they were not necessarily as important as the image on the screen. This is an important exercise as students need to be able to engage with the technological tools and interventions provided to them, but they must also be able to engage with the content itself without being distracted by the interventions. Six of the L1 participants (i.e., 85.71%) and both of the L2 participants had no issue

remembering the visual information they were asked about in question 2. This correlates with their fixation data in both the gaze plot and the heat map that were generated based on this section of the video (Figures 5 and 6).

Figure 5.
Gaze Plot for Question 2

Figure 6.
Heat Map for Question 2

As can be seen in Figure 5, the participants' attention was mostly focused on the presenter's hands and not on the subtitles on the screen. In this case, the subtitles only acted as a transcription of what was said in the video and did not contain any important terminology. Because their fixations were on the presenter's actions, the participants were able to recall them. However, this data could also be an example of the fact that the subtitles did not distract the participants from important information that was being relayed on the screen (Vanderplank, 1988). Therefore, the subtitles were clearly not a hindrance to their comprehension and recall in this instance. The heat map generated by *Tobii Pro Lab* solidifies these findings. As is visible in Figure 6, the participants largely fixated on the actions of the presenter in the video when it was required of them, and their fixation duration on the subtitles was shorter, showing that they were not distracted by the presence of the subtitles in this instance.

Both of the L2 participants in the study also managed to answer question 2 of the questionnaire correctly. While the heat map distribution of the L2 participants' viewing activity is very similar to the distribution in Figure 6, the gaze plot produced by the L2 participants' viewing activity in the context of question 2 is interesting. As can be seen in Figure 7, P1 (L2) (indicated in pink) fixated on the subtitles for some time; however, as indicated by the numbers inside the fixation circles, the subtitles were one of the last things they looked at in this instance. P2 (L2) (indicated in blue), however, did not consider the subtitles at all. This could show that even with translated subtitles, the participants were not distracted from important information being disseminated on the screen.

Figure 7.

Gaze Plot for Afrikaans-Subtitled Video's Content in Relation to Question 2

Figure 8.

Heat Map for English-Subtitled Video's Content Pertaining to Question 3

Question 3 of the questionnaire serves a similar purpose to question 2 and will, therefore, not be discussed at length. The goal of the question was to determine whether participants were able to recall subtler information in the video, even if subtitles were present. Five of the L1 participants (71.43%) managed to answer question 3 correctly. Interestingly, this was a section of the video where one of the L2 participants, once again, decided to engage only with the English subtitles and did not view the Afrikaans subtitles at all. The L2 participants' results were thus excluded for this question. The heat map of the L1 participants' viewing patterns illustrates the reason for this (Figure 8 above). As illustrated in Figure 8, the participants mostly did not focus on the presenter's face for long but rather on important terms in the subtitles—e.g., 'palpate' and 'omasum'. In spite of this, they were largely able to recall the subtle detail that the presenter wore glasses, showing once again that they were not overly distracted by the subtitles (cf. Vanderplank, 1988).

Figure 9.
*Gaze Plot for the English-Subtitled
Video's Content in Question 4*

Figure 10.
*Gaze Plot for the Afrikaans-Subtitled
Video's Content in Question 4*

The fourth and fifth questions in the post-video questionnaire (Appendix A) served similar purposes—i.e., to determine whether the subtitles in the video promote comprehension and language acquisition among students. The participants were introduced to new discipline-specific terms, and these questions sought to measure their ability to engage with, recall, and understand the introduced terms. The participants' responses to questions 4 and 5 indicated that, once again, only one of the L2 participants made use of the Afrikaans subtitles for question 5. The responses of the L2 participants were, therefore, not taken into account for question 5; however, they did yield usable data in their responses to question 4. Six of the L1 participants (85.71%) answered question 4 correctly, while only one of the L2 participants answered question 4 correctly. However, only two of the L1 participants (28.57%) managed to answer question 5 correctly.

Figures 9 and 10 (above) show gaze plots of the L1 and L2 participants' viewing activity in relation to question 4. Figure 9 indicates that the L1 participants' focus was mixed: some focused on the important term ('Peyer's patches') in the subtitles, while most focused on the structure itself as it appeared on the screen. The participants' fixation on the subtitles was also short, as indicated by the smaller fixation circles shown in Figure 9. However, the L1 participants were still largely able to answer question 4 correctly, which required them to simply remember whether the Peyer's patches were shown in the video. This question required a simple yes/no response from the participants, and their engagement with and fixation on the structure on the screen enabled them to respond correctly.

The researcher puts forward that P1 (L2) was able to respond correctly to question 4 because of the participant's balanced engagement with the on-screen image and the subtitles. Figure 10 shows that P1 (L2) (indicated in yellow) spent some time fixating on the subtitles relating to question 4, while P2 (L2) (indicated in red) did not consider the subtitles at all and could not respond to question 4 correctly. In this context, the subtitles were useful, in terms of subject matter recall, to the L2 participant who made use of them.

The participants' responses to question 5, however, differ rather drastically from question 4. As previously noted, only 28.57% managed to answer question 5 correctly. There are a number of possible reasons for this. Firstly, the question was not as straightforward as question 4 and required the participants to remember the Latin name of a structure that was discussed in the video. This required them not only to recall what they saw in the video but also to understand its content. Secondly, question 5 was phrased in a more complex way than question 4. The phrasing of the question required the participants to carefully consider their answers and think back on the content of the video before providing a response.

Lastly, as shown in Figure 11 below, the participants focused mainly on the structure shown on the screen and not on the subtitles. Figure 11 illustrates that only P1 (indicated in pink) and P2 (indicated in light blue) fixated on the subtitles relating to question 5. P7 (indicated in dark red) only fixated on the subtitles for a short time, but P7's attention did not return to the subtitles. The researcher puts forward that P1 and P2 were able to answer question 5 correctly because they fixated on and returned to the subtitles, and this allowed them to engage with, recall, and understand the subject matter in its context. Figure 12 below is a heat map of the participants' viewing activity relating to question 5. The heat map in Figure 12 illustrates how P1 and P2 fixated on both the subtitles and the structure shown on the screen. In terms of P1 and P2's fixations on the subtitles, the participants tended to pay no attention to known words ('that', 'is', 'the') and fixated only on the newer, more

unfamiliar term in the subtitle (*'recessus supraomentalis'*). The researcher therefore puts forward that, as correlated by Figures 11 and 12, P1 and P2 were able to answer question 5 correctly because they focused specifically on the important terminology in the subtitle in conjunction with the structure discussed on the screen.

Figure 11.
*Gaze Plot for the English-Subtitled
Video's Content in Question 5*

Figure 12.
*Heat Map for the English-Subtitled
Video's Content in Question 5*

5. Conclusion

The use of subtitling and eye-tracking technology has shown great potential in promoting comprehension and language acquisition in multilingual settings. The research findings in this context have highlighted the effectiveness of subtitling and eye-tracking technology in facilitating language acquisition and comprehension. One of the major advantages of subtitling is that it provides an effective means of improving the subject matter recall skills of individuals in multilingual settings. Subtitling can help learners understand the context and meaning of unfamiliar words by providing visual cues. This is illustrated in Figure 13 (below), which summarises the number of correct versus incorrect answers provided by the L1 and L2 participants in the study in conjunction with the subtitle interaction each question received. As is shown in Figure 13, the participants were often more likely to answer a question correctly if they had engaged with the subtitles. There were some questions where the subtitles were not the focus of the question; therefore, the participants' subtitle interaction did not necessarily link to their ability to answer the question correctly (e.g., questions 2 and 3). However, the results show that subtitling can be beneficial to students' comprehension and language acquisition—especially in multilingual settings—even though the sample size for this study was small. As a 'washback', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2021b), of this study, it can be argued that eye-tracking in subtitled videos can be beneficial when

considering how individuals process information and comprehend language, as their viewing activity and subtitle interaction can be very clearly measured.

Figure 13.

Participants' Correct/Incorrect Responses to the Questionnaire

Moreover, the use of subtitling and eye-tracking technology can also promote inclusivity in multilingual settings. These technologies can be used to provide access to content for individuals who are deaf or hard of hearing or those who are not English L1 speakers. Although the isiZulu and Sepedi subtitles were not used by the participants in this study, they are still useful and necessary for English L2 speakers, especially in higher learning institutions where English is the main medium of instruction.

Despite the numerous benefits of subtitling and eye-tracking technology, there are also some limitations that need to be considered. One limitation of subtitling is that it can be distracting for some individuals; however, this study has shown, albeit with a small sample size, that most viewers do not experience subtitles as a distraction. The small sample size available to the researcher is another limitation that must be considered. The data gathered in this research is, unfortunately, not representative of a large population, but it does provide valuable insights into how subtitles may be applied in the 'panopticon', à la Salmani Nodoushan (2023), of academic settings to promote subject matter comprehension and language acquisition among students.

All in all, this study has indicated that the use of subtitling and eye-tracking technology has shown great potential in promoting comprehension and

language acquisition in multilingual settings. These technologies can be used to improve subject matter recall, aid in vocabulary acquisition, promote comprehension, and provide access to content for individuals who are deaf, hard of hearing, or not English L1 speakers without imposing a high cognitive load on viewers. Nevertheless, it is important to consider the limitations of the study and address these limitations in order to promote the accessibility and effectiveness of subtitling as a practice and eye-tracking technology as a tool to measure the effectiveness of subtitling. Further research is needed to explore the full potentials and 'affordances' (cf. Salmani Nodoushan, 2021a) of subtitling and eye-tracking technology in promoting language acquisition and comprehension in multilingual settings, specifically with larger, more representative sample sizes.

Notes:

1. For more detailed discussion of these and other related topics, see Balosa (2024), Chaka (2024), Huang (2024), Kruger-Marais (2024), Mapuya (2024), Motaung (2024), Ndlangamandla (2024), Ndlangamandla et al. (2024), Nkhi and Shange (2024), Salmani Nodoushan (2024), and Xu and Fang (2024).

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Appendix A: Post-Video Questionnaire

1. What is the cavity between the teeth and the tongue of an animal called?
 - A. *Cavum oris*
 - B. *Cavum nasi*
 - C. Uvula
 - D. Soft palate

2. When the presenter discusses palpation, can you remember whether he palpates the animal's lumbar region with one hand, or both hands?
 - A. He uses one hand
 - B. **He uses both hands**

3. Does the presenter wear glasses in this video?
 - A. **Yes, he does**
 - B. No, he does not

4. Are the Peyer's patches ever shown in this video?
 - A. No, they are not shown
 - B. **Yes, they are shown**

5. The cavity which contains the animal's small and large intestines, as well as the uterus in a pregnant female animal, is called:
 - A. *Duodenum*
 - B. *Jejunum*
 - C. ***Recessus supraomentalis***
 - D. *Ostium intra pharyngeum*